

Yield performance at different Nepalese research stations, agronomic characteristics, and responses to diseases and insects of 4 new rice varieties in Nepal, 1978.^a

	Laxami	Durga	Janaki	Sabitri	Panvanipur-1 (check)	Chandina (check)	Masuli (check)
<i>Mean yield (t/ha)</i>							
Kankai	5183	5923	4323	3703	5736	4697	3121
Tarhara	6060	6284	5286	3918	6914	5990	3854
Janakpur	4128	5098	4717	4893	4585	4243	4797
Parwanipur	4585	4974	3883	3405	4362	3915	2548
Rampur	2800	3429	4001	4053	3949	3000	3164
Bhainva	4758	4477	3905	4196	2922	5430	3240
Nepalganj	5113	4696	5126	3722	5861	4708	4042
Av	4777	5016	4404	3995	4804	4794	3564
<i>Agronomic characteristics</i>							
Days to heading	88	100	104	90	106	111	121
Days to maturity	111	128	134	120	135	140	150
Plant ht (cm)	93	91	92	80	98	94	120
Tillers (no.)	6.5	6.5	7.0	8.0	9.0	9.0	9.5
1,000 grain wt (g)	23	25	26	20	27	25	17
Milling recovery (%)	72.5	66.5	—	70	67	73	—
Head rice (%)	79.0	86.5	—	81.9	79.9	91.8	—
Protein (%)	6.9	1.3	—	7.0	5.5	8.0	—
Grain quality	Coarse	Medium	Coarse	Medium	Coarse	Medium	Medium fine
<i>Response to diseases^b and insects^c</i>							
Blast	1	1	1-2	1-5	1-3	1-3	1-6
Bacterial blight	3-5	3-5	7-9	3	1-3	3-5	3-5
Brown spot	3	3	3	3	1-3	1-7	3-5
Sheath blight	—	MR	—	—	MS	—	—
Brown planthopper	MR	S	S	—	—	R	—
Green leafhopper	R	R	S	—	—	R	—
Gall midge	—	MR	—	—	MR	—	R

^aVarieties Laxami and Durga were tested in Mar-Jun along with check varieties Parwanipur-1 and Chandina; Janaki and Sabitri were tested against Masuli (Mahsuli) during Jun-Nov, the normal season.

^bOn a scale of 1-9 of the 1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

^cMR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, R = resistant.

Laxami and Durga yield better than the recommended varieties in the early season, and their early maturity leaves farmers enough time to grow a second

crop. The two also have better resistance to insects and diseases than other recommended varieties. Durga and Sabitri have good eating quality and

medium-fine grain. All four varieties have high response to fertilizer, lodging resistance, and improved plant type (see table).■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Cooking characteristics of selected IR424 lines

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Basmati rice is well known for grain and cooking qualities and for aroma. It is used in the preparation of delicacies on festive occasions and its long grain brings a special market price; however, it has poor plant type and yields low.

Crosses were made during the mid-1960s at IRRI to improve its plant type and thus its yield potential, while keeping its other qualities intact.

From materials originally received from IRRI, 119 lines of the IR424 cross (Basmati 370*³/TN1) were selected at BRRI. The lines were grown in observational trials in the 1978 boro (Dec-May) at BRRI. Fifteen lines were selected for their grain yield and cooking quality. Cooking quality was further evaluated on the basis of elongation ratio

(av length of 10 randomly selected cooked grains to av length of 10 randomly selected uncooked grains), imbibition ratio (vol of cooked to vol of uncooked grains), visual scoring of cooked grains, and aroma.

Twenty-five polished grains were cooked for 7 minutes in 20 ml boiling water. The cooked grains were transferred to petri dishes and visually scored for uniformity of length and smoothness. The cooked samples were also checked for aroma. BR5, BR7, and Kataribhog

were used as checks. BR5 has fine aromatic grains. BR7 has long nonaromatic grains; Kataribhog has long aromatic grains but unsatisfactory yield.

Most of the lines varied widely in the visual scores — only 15 were scored 3 to 5 and none were scored 1. Fifty lines scored 7 and 54 lines, 9. Variability was observed for all characters studied. The table lists 15 selections equivalent to or better than the standard checks. All of the selected lines had numerically higher elongation-ratio values than the checks. But 12 selections had similar or higher imbibition ratio values, and most were equivalent to the checks in visual scores. ■

Elongation ratio, imbibition ratio, and visual score of selected aromatic IR424 lines. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1978.

Pedigree	Elongation ratio	Imbibition ratio	Visual score ^a
IR424-2-1			
/J1-30-6	2.00	3.98	3
/J1-30-7	1.98	3.95	3
/J1-30-8	1.88	3.76	3
/J7-2-4	1.85	3.69	3
/J7-2-5	1.75	3.77	3
/J7-2-7	1.85	2.61	5
/J7-2-9	1.85	3.69	3
/J7-2-15	1.85	2.74	5
/J7-4-11	1.76	2.52	5
/J7-4-14	1.82	3.62	3
/J7-4-15	2.00	4.31	3
/J8-1-8	2.07	4.47	3
/J8-1-9	2.00	3.98	3
/J8-1-18	2.01	4.35	3
/J8-7-14	1.88	4.07	3
BR5	1.70	3.58	3
BR7 ^b	1.40	3.60	3
Kataribhog	1.67	4.18	3

^a1 = All cooked grains smooth and uniform in length; 3 = 80% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 5 = 60% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 7 = 40% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 9 = 20% cooked grains smooth, uniform.

^bNonaromatic.

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Rice cultures that are moderately resistant to Helminthosporiose

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Helminthosporiose is widespread in Tamil Nadu. The disease affects the [rice crop at all growth stages; no cultivated variety is resistant or tolerant. The 540 IET entries received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for reaction to high pressure of helminthosporiose in a semidry nursery. The entries were grown in 2 rows, 1 In long, surrounded by 1 row of the susceptible check Benibhog. At 45 days of age the plants were spray inoculated with a conidial suspension (concn of 40,000 spores/ml) of *Helminthosporium oryzae* that had been isolated from typical lesions. The disease incidence was scored on a 0-9 scale. Benibhog had a score of 9 (highly susceptible) and many entries scored from 5 to 7. Five entries — IET5870, IET5878, IET6515, IET6524, and IET6541 — were scored from 0 to 1. When tested in the laboratory under similar inoculum pressure, the cultures showed moderate resistance to the disease (score, lower than 3). ■

Resistance of cultivars to the rice leaf folder

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Eleven standard cultivars and four promising lines were evaluated for resistance to the rice leaf folder in a randomized block design replicated three times in a field trial in 1977 kharif. In the last week of August, when leaf folder incidence was at a peak, all the leaves and those infested on 15 hills/replication

were counted and the percentage of infestation was recorded.

Infestation ranged from 13 to 63%; it was highest on Jaya and lowest on Prasad (see table). No cultivar was immune to leaf folder attack. ■

Susceptibility of rice cultivars to the rice leaf folder. Pantnagar, India.

Designation	Av infestation (%)
Jaya	63
IR8	61
Padma	57
UPR190D-17-1	55
IR20	52
UPR173-23	49
UPR82-1-7	49
Cauvery	42
Bala	38
Saket-4	36
Tilak chandan (dwarf (mutant))	31
Ratna	30
Pusa 2-21	24
IR24	15
Prasad	13
CD at 5%	17.55

Straighthead disease of rice suspected in southern Thailand

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Severe symptoms similar to those of straighthead disease reported in the USA and Japan were observed in southern Thailand in 1977. The observations were made in an 80-ha area of lowland rice planted on sandy soil that was previously planted to upland crops in Ronphibool subprovince, Nakornsrithamaraj province. The rice plants were at the heading stage, The infected plants had normal vegetative growth but exhibited tillering at the upper nodes, poor exertion, twisted spikelets, distorted hulls (in “parrot beak” shape), and high sterility.